

Physico-Chemical Properties and Microbial Community of Soils Polluted by Tannery Effluents at the Nigerian Institute of Leather and Science Technology Zaria, Nigeria

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Abstract

Tannery effluent is a wastewater containing complex toxic chemical compounds affecting the environment and the exposed organisms. This study is aimed to evaluate the physicochemical parameters and microbial composition of soil contaminated by tannery effluents. The results showed that the contaminated soil recorded highest levels of chromium and ammonia in site C, which ranges from a minimum of 0.40mg/g to a maximum of 0.43mg/g and lowest concentration of 0.60 to a maximum of 0.70mg/g respectively. Similarly, sulphide ranges from 0.40 mg/g concentration to 0.44mg/g in the same site. The recorded values exceeded the tolerable levels of <0.1, 0.2 and 0.2 mg/g for chromium, ammonia and sulphide respectively, set by Federal Ministry of Environment. Additionally, the results revealed variety of bacteria inhabiting the contaminated soil, such as *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Serratia marcescens*, and *Streptococcus pyogenes*. Moreover, the fungal species analysed in the contaminated soil includes *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium notatum*, *Mucor pusillus* and *Fusarium sporotrichioides*. High counts of bacteria and fungi were recorded in the soil contaminated with tannery effluent. The viable soil microbial counts were found in the range of $7.90 \pm 1.60 - 8.00 \pm 0.70 \times 10^5$ cfu/g and $1.50 \pm 0.10 - 1.2 \pm 0.20 \times 10^4$ cfu/g for the bacteria and fungi, respectively. The presence of these chemical substances and microorganisms in the contaminated soil samples poses a potential threat to environmental sustainability. Future research should focus on sustainable waste disposal solutions and evaluate the long-term ecological impacts of tannery-related pollution.

Keywords: Microorganism, physicochemical parameters, polluted soil, Tannery effluent

1.0 Introduction

Tannery effluent is defined as the wastewater resulting from the industrial processes of transformation of animal skins and hides into leather. This effluent is mainly characterized by a complex mixture of organic wastes, hazardous substances, as well as metallic and non-metallic pollutants.¹ These constituents often led to dark brown colour and a characteristics foul smell.² Tannery operations poses significant threat to the environment and the health of other organisms exposed to polluted environment, including humans and animals. However, these wastes contain a variety of chemicals that are used in the tanning process, such as sodium sulphide, chromium sulphate, and non-ionic wetting agents, which may

accumulate in the immediate ecosystems of the tannery local environment.³ The high sulphide content of tannery effluents apart from being toxic to humans, may also pose serious odour to the environment. Furthermore, chromium content may pose great danger to human health at a low concentration level of 0.1mg/l.²

The accumulation of contaminated water in soil reduces oxygen availability, limiting its role as an electron acceptor and promoting anaerobic respiration pathways such as denitrification, during which nitrate is microbially reduced to gaseous nitrogen species, including nitrous oxide (N₂O), which is subsequently emitted to the atmosphere and contributes to greenhouse gas fluxes.^{4,5} Discharge of untreated

tannery effluents significantly alters soil physicochemical properties (such as pH, temperature, salts, organic load), creating anaerobic microenvironments and disrupting microbial communities, which can stimulate methanogenic archaea and enhance methane (CH₄) production, to a potent greenhouse gas contributing to global warming above baseline levels.^{6,7,8}

The tannery section of the Nigerian Institute of Leather and Science Technology (NILEST), Zaria, Nigeria, is situated close to administrative offices, thereby exposing staff and the surrounding public to obnoxious odours, toxic chemicals, and potentially pathogenic microorganisms associated with tannery operations.^{9,10} Tannery effluents are known to contain high organic loads, sulphides, ammonia, chromium, and other heavy metals that significantly alter soil physicochemical properties, including pH, electrical conductivity, organic carbon, and nutrient balance.^{11,12} These changes can profoundly influence soil microbial community structure, favouring metal-tolerant and opportunistic microorganisms, some of which may pose public-health risks.^{9,10} Moreover, leaching of untreated tannery effluents into subsurface soils can contaminate groundwater resources, increasing the risk of human exposure through drinking-water pathways.¹³ Therefore, the objective of this study was to determine the physicochemical properties and microbial composition of soils impacted by tannery activities at NILEST, Zaria.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample Collection

Sample collection was carried out in accordance with the method described by.¹⁴ Soil samples were collected at a depth 10 cm from three different locations at the tannery polluted soil, which labelled as sample A, B and C, respectively. Samples were collected three times in a month at intervals of 10 days, from June and July, 2025. All samples were placed in a sterile polythene bag to prevent contamination and to preserve soil properties, and immediately transported to the Quality control and Microbiology laboratory of the NILEST for analysis. But for the control, soil sample (sample D) was collected from residential area in the institute.

2.2 Media used

The culture media used in this study included Nutrient agar, Sabouraud dextrose agar, and MacConkey agar.

Nutrient agar and Sabouraud dextrose agar were obtained from Fluka Biochemica (Germany), while MacConkey agar was obtained from Antec (UK). All media were prepared and sterilized in accordance with the manufacturers' instructions and standard microbiological procedures, as described by Atlas.^{15,16}

2.3 Determination of Soil pH

Soil pH was determined using an analytical instrument pH meter-2603. Exactly 10 g of the soil sample was placed in a beaker containing 10 ml of distilled water, stirred, and allowed to stand for 30 minutes. To ensure accurate functioning of the pH meter, the instrument was calibrated using standard buffer solutions before measurement. The electrode of the pH meter was then inserted into the mixture, and the pH readings were recorded.¹⁷

2.4 Determination of soil temperature

Soil temperature was measured at the point of sample collection using a mercury-in-glass soil thermometer (Bent Soil Thermometer) following standard procedures.¹⁸ The thermometer bulb was inserted vertically into the soil to a depth of 10 cm and allowed to equilibrate before recording the temperature.

2.5 Determination of soil phosphorus

Phosphorus content of the soil samples was determined using the vanado-molybdophosphoric acid colorimetric method following standard procedures.¹⁹ In this method, phosphate ions reacted with ammonium molybdate and ammonium metavanadate under acidic conditions to form a yellow-coloured vanado-molybdophosphoric acid complex. The phosphorus concentration was measured using a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 490 nm.

2.6 Determination of soil sulphide

Sulphide content was determined using a classical gravimetric method following a described procedure.¹⁹ Exactly, 2 cm³ of concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl) was added to 100 cm³ of the soil sample, and the mixture was heated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in 5 cm³ of concentrated HCl, and the insoluble portion was filtered off and washed with distilled water. The filtrate was diluted to 100 cm³ with distilled water, and the pH was adjusted to 4.5 using acetate buffer. The solution was reheated to boiling until precipitation was formed, before digested at 80 °C for 3 h, filtered, dried, and weighed

to constant weight in a pre-weighed evaporating dish. Sulphur content was calculated gravimetrically from the mass of barium sulphate precipitate obtained after digestion and drying to constant weight using the stoichiometric relationship between sulphur and barium sulphate.

2.7 Determination of soil ammonia

Ammonium (NH_4^+) content in soil samples polluted by tannery effluents was determined using the Macro-Kjeldahl method as described.²⁰ Exactly 2 g of the soil sample was weighed into an 800 ml Kjeldahl flask. A catalyst mixture ($\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4\text{CuSO}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) weighing 2 g and 30 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) were added, and the contents were thoroughly mixed and heated until complete digestion of organic matter was achieved, as indicated by the appearance of a light grey solution. After cooling, 50 ml of distilled water was added and shaken. The digest was then subjected to distillation. Exactly 20 ml of boric acid mixed indicator solution was placed in a Kjeldahl flask, followed by 20 ml of 40% sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution was added, and distillation was carried out. A total of 40 ml of distillate was collected and titrated against a standard acid solution. The ammonium content was calculated according to the standard Kjeldahl procedure.²⁰

2.8 Determination of soil magnesium and chromium

Magnesium and chromium concentrations in soil samples polluted by tannery effluents were determined using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS) following standard procedures.¹⁹ Stock solutions (1000 ppm) of magnesium and chromium were prepared, and a series of calibration standards were obtained by appropriate serial dilution. For sample preparation, 100 cm^3 of each soil extract was digested with concentrated hydrochloric acid and nitric acid in a ratio of 3:1. The digests were filtered and diluted to 250 cm^3 with distilled water. A blank solution was prepared by subjecting 100 cm^3 of distilled water to the same digestion procedure. Magnesium and chromium concentrations were determined by aspirating the calibration standards, samples, and blank into the AAS at wavelengths of 285.2 nm for magnesium and 425.4 nm for chromium, respectively.

2.9 Determination of soil calcium

Calcium concentrations were determined using flame emission spectrophotometry in accordance with standard procedures described by.¹⁹ Stock solution (1000 ppm) of calcium was prepared, and a series of working calibration standard was obtained by appropriate serial dilutions. The blank, calibration standards, and sample solutions were aspirated into the flame photometer fitted with specific calcium interference filter. Calcium concentrations in the samples were quantified using calibration curve generated from the standard solution.

2.10 Microbial analysis

The microbial analysis was carried out according to a described method.²¹ Exactly 1g of the soil sample collected at the tannery local environment was serially diluted in tenfold up to 106 tubes. Then 0.1ml aliquots from the 106 tubes were inoculated onto already prepared plates of nutrient agar, MacConkey and sabouraud dextrose agars using the spread plate method of inoculation. The nutrient agar and MacConkey agar plates (for bacteria) were incubated at 37°C for 24 hrs while the sabouraud dextrose agar plates (for fungi) were incubated at ambient laboratory temperature ($28\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) for 72 hrs. Plates with distinct colonies were counted and recorded as cfu/g, after the incubation period. The colonies were also repeatedly subculture onto fresh nutrient and sabouraud dextrose agar media to obtain pure isolates. Cultural, morphological and standard biochemical tests were carried out using standard method.²² These tests include Gram stain, catalase, methyl red test, voges-proskauer test, H_2S and gas production, citrate utilization test, glucose, sucrose and lactose utilization tests, urease activity, motility, indole production, spore test and oxidase test. The fungal isolates were identified according to a described method, based on their colour of aerial hyphae and substrate mycelium, arrangement of hyphae, and conidial arrangement.²³

2.11 Data Analysis

Data analyses were conducted using descriptive statistics. The results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) to characterize the distribution and variability of the measured physicochemical parameters and microbiological plate count data was analysed using One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

3.0 Results

3.1 Physicochemical Parameter of Soil Contaminated by Tannery Effluents

The physicochemical parameters of soil samples (A, B, and C) and a control site are presented in Table 1. The soils from the contaminated sites exhibited pH values ranging from 7.1 to 7.8, with site C showing the highest alkalinity (pH 7.8) and site B the lowest (pH 7.1). The control soil recorded a pH of 6.8. All values fall within the normal soil pH range (6–9) recommended by the Federal Ministry of Environment (FMEnv), indicating that tannery effluents did not significantly alter the overall soil acidity/alkalinity, although slight variations suggest localized chemical influence at specific sites. Soil temperature was relatively uniform across the sites, with A, B, and C measuring 35°C and the control 34°C. These temperatures are within the acceptable environmental range ($\leq 40^\circ\text{C}$), suggesting that tannery operations in the locations did not seriously affect soil

thermal conditions. Chromium levels, however, were markedly elevated in the contaminated sites, ranging from 0.40 mg/g at site A to 0.43 mg/g at site C, while chromium was below detection level in the control soil. These concentrations exceed the FMEnv permissible limit of <0.1 mg/g, indicating accumulation of chromium in soils exposed to tannery effluents. Site C displayed the highest chromium concentration (0.43 mg/g), suggesting higher contamination intensity. Concentration of magnesium (0.2 mg/g) and calcium (0.2 mg/g) were relatively low in the polluted soils compared to FMEnv permissible limits (200 mg/g), with the exception of magnesium at site C (0.5 mg/g) which was higher than A and B but still below the regulatory limit. Sulphide levels in the polluted soils ranged from 0.40 to 0.44 mg/g, higher than the control (0.02 mg/g) and exceeding the FMEnv limit of 0.2 mg/g, indicating potential sulphide pollution from tannery processes. Phosphorus was below detection level in all samples, suggesting limited availability in the studied soils.

Table 1: Physicochemical parameter of soil contaminated by tannery effluents

Parameter	A	B	C	Control	FMEnvLimit
pH	7.5	7.1	7.8	6.8	6-9
Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	35.0	35	35	34.0	40
Chromium (mg/g)	0.4	0.42	0.43	BDL	<0.1
Ammonia (mg/g)	0.6	0.5	0.7	BDL	0.2
Phosphorus (mg/g)	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	5.0
Magnesium (mg/g)	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.03	200
Sulphide (mg/g)	0.42	0.40	0.44	0.02	0.2
Calcium (mg/g)	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.20	200

Key: A = soil from location A, B = Soil from location B, C = Soil from location C, BDL = Below detection levels, FMEnv = limit for physicochemical parameters.

3.2 Microbial Communities of Polluted Soil at Tannery Local Environment

A total of eight bacterial species were isolated from tannery-impacted soils, as summarized in Table 2. These included *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Serratia marcescens*, and *Streptococcus pyogenes*. The isolates exhibited diverse colonial morphologies, Gram reactions, motility, and biochemical characteristics, reflecting the heterogeneous bacterial community adapted to contaminated environments.

3.3 Morphological characteristics of fungal isolates from contaminated soil

The fungal isolates recovered from the tannery polluted soil are presented in Table 3. A total of six fungal species were identified, comprising *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium notatum*, *Mucor pusillus*, and *Fusarium sporotrichioides*. The presence of these fungal species reflects their resilience and ability to thrive in soils enriched with organic waste and tannery effluents. The presence of *Penicillium*, *Mucor*, and *Fusarium* species further indicates a diverse fungal community capable of tolerating environmental stressors, including elevated organic load and potential heavy metal contamination.

Table 2: Microbial communities of polluted soil at tannery local environment

S/N	Organism	Colonial characteristics	Gram stain	Mot	Cat	Gl	La	Ga	Su	H ₂ S	Cit	Ur	M	Ind	Sp	Ox
1	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	White small milky colonies	+Rod	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
2	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	White large colonies	+Rod	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	-
3	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	White large milky colonies	-Rod	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
4	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Blue-green colonies	-Rod	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+
5	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	Gray large colonies	-Rod	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
6	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	White small colonies	-Rod	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-
7	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	Gray large colonies	-Rod	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
8	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	Milky large rhizoid colonies	+cocci	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-

KEY: + = Positive, - = Negative, Mot = motility, Cat = catalase, Gl = glucose, La = lactose, Su = sucrose, Ox = oxidase, M = methyl red, Ind = indole, Cit = citrate, Ur = urease, Sp = spore

Table 3: Morphological characteristics of fungal isolates from contaminated soil

S/N	Isolate	Macroscopy	Microscopy	Organism
1	Fungi 1	Black and powdery-like	Canidiophores smooth walled and non-septate	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
2	Fungi 2	Whitish and colony-like	Round, black conidia, non-septate	<i>Mucor pusillus</i>
3	Fungi 3	Light green and powdery-like	Long, erect septate conidiophores	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>
4	Fungi 4	Yellowish-pink creamy colonies	Cylindrical to avoid conidia, curved septate conidiophores	<i>Fusarium sporotrichioides</i>
5	Fungi 5	Brownish colony-like	Long, erect conidiophores, round shape conidia	<i>Penicillium notatum</i>
6	Fungi 6	Gray-greenish fluffy colonies	Long, erect non-septate conidiophores	<i>Aspergillus fumigates</i>

3.4 Total viable counts of microorganisms isolated from contaminated soil

The results for total viable counts of microorganisms isolated are presented in Table 4. The results revealed that the measured parameters were consistently higher in soils from sites A, B, and C compared with the control site. For the TBC, site B recorded the highest mean value (8.10 ± 0.32), followed by sites C (8.00 ± 0.70) and A (7.90 ± 1.60), whereas the control soil exhibited a markedly lower value (2.50 ± 0.14). Similarly, the TFC showed elevated concentrations in the contaminated sites, with site A having the highest mean value (1.50 ± 0.10), followed by sites B (1.33 ± 0.04) and C (1.20 ± 0.20). The lowest concentration was observed at the control site (1.00 ± 0.02). Overall, the results indicate a clear enrichment of these microorganisms in soils from the impacted sites relative to the control.

Table 4: Total viable counts of microorganisms isolated from contaminated soil

S/N	Soil sample	TBC \pm SD ($\times 10^5$ cfu/g)	TFC \pm SD ($\times 10^4$ cfu/g)
1	A	7.90 \pm 1.60	1.50 \pm 0.10
2	B	8.10 \pm 0.32	1.33 \pm 0.04
3	C	8.00 \pm 0.70	1.20 \pm 0.20
4	Control	2.50 \pm 0.14	1.00 \pm 0.02

Key: TBC = Total bacterial count, TFC = Total fungal count, cfu/g- Colony forming unit per gramme, A = soil from point A, B = Soil from point B and C = Soil from point C.

4.0 Discussion

The findings for most of the physicochemical parameters are higher compared to the limit set by FME_{env}. The slightly higher pH value maybe the reason for the high counts of microorganisms obtained from all the sampling locations because most microorganisms thrive well at such pH value (6-9).²⁴The pH could also further enhance microbial degradation of the contents of the effluents. The

values of sulphide, ammonia and chromium obtained in this study were higher than threshold limits 0.2mg/g for sulphide and ammonia, while <0.1mg/g for chromium reported by the Federal Ministry of Environment. The highest level of sulphide obtained could be as a result of the use of sulphuric acid or chemical substances with high content of sodium sulphate in tanning process.

The high level of ammonia may retard the oxidation of nitrite in the soil and promote nitrite accumulation in the soil. The results in the present study are in agreement with that earlier finding reported.²⁵ Similarly, sulphide and ammonia levels were reported in textile industries' effluents exceeding the limits set by Federal Ministry of Environment.²⁶ The values of chromium obtained in this study are not surprising because chromium salt is used in tanning process, which indicates environmental pollution in the tannery environment. These hazardous elements may also enter the food chain through plants, animals, as well as surface water source through surface runoff. Once it gets into aquatic food chains, it bioaccumulate and biomagnified to various trophic levels and subsequently reaching human population. This result was in conformity with that of²⁷, which reported that bioconcentration and bioaccumulation could lead to toxic levels and affecting the health of organisms even if the exposed to low level toxicity. This could also cause disruption in the ecological balance when in abundance.

The microorganisms identified in contaminated soil revealed high concentrations of both bacterial and fungal flora. Fewer microbial counts recorded from control soil samples. However, data analysis of all the parameters tested in the sampling sites showed no difference between the parameters. Most of the organisms isolated are indigenous to soil environments, however, their presence in this study may be attributed to the discharge of the tannery effluents into the surrounding soil.

The present finding is in strong agreement with previous studies that reported similar bacterial consortia, including *Pseudomonas* spp., *Klebsiella* spp., and *Escherichia coli* associated with tannery effluent contamination, as well as fungi such as *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus* spp. predominating in impacted soils due to their resilience and capacity to tolerate complex pollutants.^{27,28} The presence of *Aspergillus* species in soil affected by industrial effluents is supported by recent work demonstrating the adaptability and bioremediation potential of *A.*

niger and related fungi in tannery wastewater environments.²⁹ Similarly, high concentrations and variety of bacteria and fungi including *E. coli*, *Proteus* sp., *Streptococcus* sp., and *Aspergillus niger* have been documented in effluent-affected matrices, highlighting significant public health implications due to the occurrence of potentially pathogenic microbes in contaminated soils.²⁸ These findings align with broader observations that tannery-affected and industrially polluted soils often harbor both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria as well as tolerant fungal taxa adapted to harsh chemical conditions.^{28,29}

Elevated fungal counts in the polluted soils reflect the adaptive capacity of fungi in contaminated environments.^{27,28} Previous investigations have identified diverse fungal communities in tannery effluents and contaminated soils, including species with potential for biodegradation of tannin and other organic compounds.^{27,30} The higher total bacterial counts at the contaminated sites suggest that the increased availability of organic substrates and nutrients from tannery waste creates favourable conditions for bacterial growth.³⁰ Similar findings have been reported where bacterial populations were stimulated following disposal of tannery residues in soil, with bacteria often responding more robustly than other microbial groups due to their rapid growth rates and metabolic activities.²⁸ However, the nature of the contaminants, especially chromium, may also exert selective pressure favouring chromium-resistant microbes, as seen in other studies isolating metal-resistant bacteria from tannery-affected environments.²⁹ In contrast, the lower microbial counts observed in control soil indicate limited anthropogenic disturbance.

5.0 Conclusion

The study on physico-chemical properties and microbial community of soils polluted by tannery effluents at the NILEST Zaria, underscores the significant impact of tannery effluents on soil quality. The physicochemical analysis revealed that the soil was slightly alkaline, with pH values ranging from 7.1 to 7.8. The study also found higher concentrations of chromium, ammonia, sulphide. The results also indicate presence of microbial community of *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus* spp., *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Proteus mirabilis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Overall, the study confirms that tannery effluents contribute significantly to soil

contamination, particularly with physico-chemical parameters, which can negatively affect soil health and the environment. We therefore call for the need for effective effluent management and waste treatment to mitigate their impact on soil and surrounding ecosystems.

6.0 Recommendation

Based on the results obtained in this research, we recommend that tannery effluents generated at NILEST tannery should not be discharge into the soil without proper treatments, since it contained complex chemicals mixture that are harmful to the environment, human and can travel quite a distance within the soil. Future research should focus on sustainable waste disposal solutions and evaluate the long-term ecological impacts of tannery-related pollution.

7.0 Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest among all the authors

8.0 References

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